

ADVANTAGES OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION IN THE CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM

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Abstract. *The credit-module system is a process of educational organization, which is an assessment model based on a set of module technologies and a credit measure. Carrying it out as a whole is a complex and systematic process.*

Keywords: *credit-module system, independent education, transparency, student, process, training*

In the credit-module principle, two main issues are given importance: ensuring independent work of students; assessment of student knowledge based on rating. The following are recognized as the main tasks of the credit module system:

- organization of educational processes on the basis of modules;
- determining the value of one subject, course (credit);
- evaluation of students' knowledge based on rating points;
- to enable students to create their study plans individually;
- increase the share of independent education in the educational process;
- the convenience of educational programs and the ability to change based on the demand for a specialist in the labor market.

Pedagogical potential of the credit-module system of educational organization as a set of its possibilities (socio-cultural, systematic, organizational, legal conditionality) includes the following: availability of information, content resources; pay attention to identifying and eliminating difficulties of students and teachers in self-education activities; cooperative interaction between teacher and student, freedom to choose organizational forms, methods, means of self-education activities, the possibility of choosing the individual-personal trajectory of the student's self-education activities; includes training students' skills for various forms of independent educational activity. The pedagogical potential of the credit module system of training organization reflects the process of skill formation in their totality. At the same time, the starting point is to understand the credit (Credit, Credit-hour) as a single unit for measuring the amount of academic work of a student/teacher. One credit is equal to 1 academic hour of the student's weekly classroom work during the academic term. 2 hours (100 minutes) of independent education is conducted for each academic hour of lecture, practical (seminar) and seminar classes. The process model of forming the student's self-education activity skills in the conditions of the credit-module system of educational organization. The following are defined as methodological bases of the process model:

1. The systematic approach was chosen as the methodological basis for designing the model of the process of forming the student's independent educational activity skills in the credit-module system of the organization of education, because it is precisely this approach that clearly defines the composition of the components included in the system.

2. The implementation of the personal-activity approach allows to actively use the principle of the unity of the person and activity, to create a —successful situation. This approach works as a fact-oriented research tactic, which plays a leading role in the design of content, in the selection of forms, methods and means of forming the student's independent educational activity skills in the credit-module system of teaching.

3. The reflexive-variational approach is based on the principles of variation, support of individuality and positive outlook. The constructed model is presented in the study with interrelated components and reflects, on the one hand, the logic of the credit-module system of training organization, and on the other hand, the controlled, progressive nature, the continuity of mastery modules. Special subjects that ensure the sequence of the student's transition from the independent activity of the rating to the reflexive activity. The interaction of subjects in independent educational activity is seen on motivational/targeted, content-operational, activity rating intermediate evaluation stages and rapid and modules.

The presentation of each stage of this model allows for a consistent review of the internal content of the credit-module system of educational organization, to justify the transition from one stage to another. This model is characterized by stability, keeping the essence of the form as a whole. Consequently, the result of modeling the process of forming the student's independent educational activity skills in the credit-module system of educational organization is to separate the sequence of stages (motivational-purpose, content-operational, result-evaluation) and set between them is a relationship. It is necessary to activate the student's independent learning during the educational process. Independent education is characterized by the student's choice and implementation of the ways of setting, solving, self-monitoring and evaluation. Currently, the educational process in higher education is aimed at the comprehensive formation of specialists, and in the conditions of their acquisition of certain professional knowledge, qualifications and skills, they must carry out comprehensive systematic work on the development and management of students' cognitive activities. requires. In higher education, the teaching process should be subordinated to the acquisition of a large amount of information, the formation of effective, creative thinking, the development of the individual's intellectual potential, logical analysis and comprehensive processing of information. The content of independent education consists of independent education materials, the activities of the teacher and students. Communication between teacher and student plays a key role in this. The main tool for independent study is independent study materials. They are an integrated system, different from textbooks, teaching-methodical manuals and lecture texts. They contain deep and meaningful methodological instructions, a block for managing the learner's cognitive activity, criteria for independent study in the process of professional training, his self-directing to independent study, self- There will be psychological and pedagogical recommendations for self-control, self-expression and self-evaluation in the process of personal knowledge. Independent educational materials are in the form of instructional manuals, lecture texts, computer programs, audio and video materials, recommendations on the use of existing traditional textbooks, and other sources of information. Independent educational materials are classified according to several characteristics.

1. According to the description of the educational material:

- these are knowledge and information obtained from textbooks, educational and methodical manuals;
- additional materials; sample lecture text, etc.

2. According to the volume of educational information:

The full volume of information on the subject of the studied subject. Materials related to information technology.

3. According to the term of use:

Materials distributed to students for one-time use;

Materials that can be used several times in training.

In the process of independent learning, independent learning materials and student-teacher communication are the leading components. The level of interaction between these two components helps to balance open learning models. It should be noted that many students have never had the problem of working independently with self-study materials before. Independent educational materials, unlike textbooks, educational and methodical manuals, have a complex nature in terms of structure. Practice shows that many students cannot objectively assess their ability to work with independent educational materials during the study process. These assessments are always personal (subjective). A serious problem arises as to how to ensure the impartiality of this process. It is necessary to develop, define, justify and demonstrate the use of criteria for evaluating the ability of students to work independently with independent educational materials. Each learner chooses criteria based on his/her self-assessment and readiness to adjust or organize his/her activities. Today, developed countries have accumulated a lot of experience in using pedagogical technologies that increase the educational and creative activities of students and guarantee the effectiveness of the educational process, and interactive methods form the basis of this experience. The student mainly demonstrates the knowledge he has mastered, and the teacher listens to his thoughts, where necessary, the teacher-student interview participants in traditional education ask questions. In conclusion, all the qualities mentioned above change with age. Independent and critical thinking is necessary in creative work, which ensures the productivity of mental activity. In the process of education, non-traditional methods prepare the ground for all-round development of the student's personality. It is worth noting that the students whom we educate and educate today are of great importance in determining the future and destiny of our country.

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